

THE ROLE OF STANDARDIZATION IN THE INDUSTRY AND THE ANALYTICAL METHODS OF PRODUCT CERTIFICATION

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Abstract. *In accordance with the requirements of the International Organization for Standardization and other organizations, standards are used in order for manufacturers to enter consumer markets or foreign markets and increase their competitiveness. For international standards and national standards of foreign countries, as well as for models of international rules and norms, the installation, parameters, dimensions and quality of the normative unit also includes production technology, testing and control methods, product placement, design and storage. Product certification is carried out to assess the conformity of product characteristics, to verify the product's compliance with the technical and legal requirements of the relevant market.*

Keywords: *standardization, management metrology, certification, progressive, safety, trade, measurement, model, comparison, import, marking.*

Pursuant to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 12, 2018 PQ-4059 "On measures for further development of technical regulation, standardization, certification and metrology systems"

This Law defines the legal, economic and organizational basis of certification of products, services and other objects, including production processes, management systems, and specialists who apply for participation as employees in the field of conformity assessment, as well as the rights, obligations and responsibilities of certification participants. In the law, the concept of state standard is changed to the concept of "national standard" based on foreign experiences, as it means mandatory implementation. Because national standards are set to be applied on a voluntary basis.

The main purpose of international standards is to create a unified methodological basis for the development of new quality systems at the international level and the improvement of existing quality systems and their certification. Scientific and technical cooperation in the field of standardization is aimed at coordinating the national standardization system with international, regional and progressive national standardization systems Both backward countries and developed countries are equally interested in international standardization. The following categories of normative documents on standardization are used in the Republic of Uzbekistan: international (interstate, regional) standards, state standards, organization standards, national standards of foreign countries.

Conformity assessment, testing, inspection necessary to ensure compliance of products, materials, services and systems with the requirements established in standards, regulatory documents, legal documents and contractual agreements in order to ensure consumer confidence, life safety and quality. and is a common activity performed in calibrations Today, it has a significant impact on the global economy, because it predicts the acceptance and rejection of objects, which directly affects risk analysis, business decisions, and costs of Product certification

is carried out to assess the conformity of product characteristics, to verify the product's compliance with the technical and legal requirements of the relevant market. The aim is mainly to ensure the appropriate quality and safety of the products. Certified products receive a license that allows the use of the respective brandreputation and financial transactions. makes a secret.

Figure 1 - Test results and their measurement uncertainties with respect to the upper limit value

Four specific case examples (options A to D in Figure 1) can be used to consider the different scenarios that can be explored when assessing compliance based on quantitative results. In this case, options A and D lead to an unambiguous decision that is not affected by the uncertainty of measurements. In accordance with the requirements of the World Trade Organization, the International Organization for Standardization and other organizations, standards are used on a voluntary basis so that manufacturers can enter consumer markets or foreign markets and increase their competitiveness.

Product certification includes risk analysis, product testing in an accredited laboratory, comparison of properties, and monitoring of product quality throughout the validity period of the certificate.

Product certification is recommended to all manufacturing companies that seek to guarantee the required quality and compliance of their products with relevant requirements.

Based on the Law on Standardization, the standardization system regulates the general organizational and technical rules of conducting standardization works. Normative documents on standardization are based on modern achievements of science and technology of our country and abroad.

They should not create excessive obstacles for international trade. It is not allowed to produce and sell products without regulatory documents. In order to ensure the competitiveness of the manufactured product, in reasonable cases, preliminary requirements based on the capabilities of traditional technologies are set in the standards. If the test method requires that the permissible error in drying the sample does not exceed 10 °C, then it is possible to carry out measurements with a measuring tool with a certified permissible error of at least 3 °C. (250 \pm 10) °C or the measurement result is between 240 °C and 260 °C.

(250 °C) °C or 247 °C to 253 °C when using the 6G method. In this case, it is possible to ensure the reliability of the measurements, and it is enough that the measuring instrument works within the limits of its permissible error. In this case, there is no need to estimate the measurement uncertainty.

Tools for observing and monitoring the conditions of testing processes

If it is ensured that the accuracy and reliability of the test is not significantly affected by the environment, it is possible to use the measuring tools used in the monitoring of environmental conditions in the specified order.

At the same time, the decision-making on the suitability of the measuring instrument by the reference laboratories should be approved taking into account the requirements of ILAC-G8:09/2019.

Basis: Clause 5.2 of Manual ILAC-G8:09/2019.

RECOMMENDATIONS:	
Size determination:	Through the display of the measuring tool
Determination of quantities in the model (formula).	NO FORMULA
The condition of observability in the measuring instrument:	Availability of a calibration or comparison certificate
Whether a benchmarking certificate will suffice:	YES. Condition: 1. The comparison certificate must have a statement showing the actual values; 2. The accuracy of the measuring instrument in the comparison certificate should be at least 3 times more accurate than the accuracy specified in the test method
Whether a measurement uncertainty assessment is required for the test report:	Not rated
A method of calculating the cumulative standard uncertainty uc in the test process	Not rated
A method for estimating the extended uncertainty U in the test process	Not rated

A standard is a document that applies to various types of activities or their results, defines rules, general principles or descriptions for general and multiple use, and aims to achieve the most optimal level of regulation in a specific field. standardization is an activity aimed at achieving the most optimal level of regulation in a specific field, defining rules for general and multiple use in relation to existing or expected tasks. technical committee on standardization is a consultative body participating in the implementation of the development of the standardization system in the areas of activity. object of standardization - products, goods, services (hereinafter referred to as products), processes, management systems, terms, conventional signs, research (testing), measurement (including selection of samples) and testing methods, labeling, conformity evaluation procedures and other objects. international (regional) standard - a standard accepted by an international or regional standardization organization and open to the general public;

the standard of a foreign country is a standard adopted by the competent body (organization) on standardization of a foreign country. mutual agreement is a general agreement reached as a result of a process that is characterized by the absence of objections of most interested parties on existing issues and is aimed at taking into account the opinions of all parties and bringing together incompatible points of view. Expensive branded products are everywhere. New companies seem to pop up overnight. Product certification is one of your best tools for distinguishing questionable or reliable quality from dangerous. Product certification lets you know that the product is safe and reliable. Reputable companies work to reduce and eliminate risk. Product certification demonstrates their commitment to quality and safety. This confirms that the products have passed specific performance and quality assurance tests. Most electronic devices are well made and reliable. Most others are done using shortcuts to make a quick profit. It can be hard to tell the difference. Product certification is an important indicator. Products without certification marks may work as intended. But they are produced cheaper. Non-certified products are mostly made from low-quality components. Components that violate product safety and quality standards if they are tested.

The specified documents must be used in accordance with the rules and procedures established in the system of certification of this type of product.

In order to ensure the competitiveness of the manufactured product, in reasonable cases, preliminary requirements based on the capabilities of traditional technologies are set in the standards. Standards for consumer products and their amendments.

To ensure the safety of the product, the environment, the life, health and property of the population, technical and informational compatibility and interchangeability of products, the unity of their control methods and the unity of labeling the requirements specified in the standards are mandatory for state administration bodies, economic activity subjects to comply with.

Copies issued by the owner of the original certificate are registered according to the document attached to the product. Each copy shows its registration number and the quantity of the product to be sold.

The management office of certification systems organizes its work on the basis of the laws and regulatory documents in force in the country, taking into account the organization of quality control of certain types of products, the mandatory requirement of compliance with standards, consumer and trade requirements. The certification office acts as a third party by conducting tests, controlling the quality of products in the enterprise and in the sales branch, organizing control, and the like.

The regional state sanitary control body, going to the place according to the established procedure, takes samples of products for conducting laboratory tests and inspects the object. Rules for marking and customs clearance of certain types of imported consumer goods, which must be marked in the state language by manufacturing enterprises, have been approved.

Import of medicines with consumer packaging (container) (code 3004 according to TIF TN) is carried out with mandatory marking in the state language. Marking of imported medicines is carried out by placing information in the national language for the consumer in the form of a leaflet on the consumer package (container), without additional marking on the package.

If there is no marking in the national language placed by the manufacturing enterprise, it is allowed to mark the imported drugs after they are brought into the territory of our republic, during storage in the customs warehouse, by placing the appropriate units of seals in the national language in the group packaging. will cry.

Each test and its results are intended to be used for certification by a third party, but are carried out by the certification office in accredited testing laboratories or its organizations authorized to conduct product tests.

Depending on the certification procedure, one type of copy of this product, a selection, or a copy of the product may be tested. Descriptions and parameters of the product, requirements for them are given in normative documents. Therefore, it allows to determine them accurately and reliably as a result of tests and measurements. Evidence proving that the product or item has undergone a certain inspection, the validity of the inspection or that it has been inspected by a certification body. a stamp, label, certificate, list to be sent as an attachment, list of certified products or list of enterprise preparers are considered.

Toxicology-hygiene exercise is a series of laboratory studies carried out on food products, which are intended for comparison with existing norms and regulations packaging materials, auxiliary materials and products made from them are means used to protect the food product from external influences during its handling. Food safety standards help prevent food contamination

In short, standardization is an activity that aims to achieve the most optimal level of regulation in a specific field, and defines rules for general and multiple use in relation to existing or expected tasks. the main goal of international standards is to create a unified methodological basis for the development of new quality systems at the international level and the improvement of existing quality systems and their certification. Scientific and technical cooperation in the field of standardization is aimed at coordinating the national standardization system with international, regional and progressive national standardization systems Both backward countries and developed countries are equally interested in international standardization Depending on the certification procedure, one type of copy of this product, a selection, or a copy of the product may be tested. Descriptions and parameters of the product, requirements for them are given in regulatory documents.

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